

THE IMPORTANCE OF STUDENT SELF-ESTEEM IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

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Abstract. *The article examines such a phenomenon as students' self-esteem in process of learning a foreign language, and also reveals the relationship between the level students' self-esteem and their academic performance.*

Key words: *self-esteem, levels of self-esteem, types of self-esteem, motivation, foreign language.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ САМООЦЕНКИ СТУДЕНТА В ПРОЦЕССЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА.

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается такое явление, как самооценка студентов в процессе изучения иностранного языка, а также выявляется связь между уровнем самооценки студентов и их успеваемостью.*

Ключевые слова: *самооценка, уровни самооценки, типы самооценки, мотивация, иностранный язык.*

Currently, researchers in the field of foreign language teaching methods languages, together with psychologists, pay great attention to factors that can significantly influence the process of teaching foreign languages. In the psychological and pedagogical literature, the affective factor is recognized as such a factor, representing the emotional component of human behavior, which in its the queue is compared with its cognitive component.

Some scientists view affective factors as emotional states personality, reflecting her attitude towards herself and communication partners [2, p. 140]. Data factors can be both stimulating and suppressive in nature, as well as determine the outcome of the learning process.

Affective factors, for example, can manifest themselves in the relationships that have developed between students and teacher, and may also be associated with the internal psychological state student. Students who have sufficient knowledge of a foreign language differ from other students the ability to control their emotional state, as well as the ability to adequately respond to difficulties arising during the learning process. In other words, various emotional factors can have a significant impact influence on the effectiveness of the process of mastering a foreign language.

Thus, it is recommended to pay special attention to the psychological aspects of teaching foreign language, since in this case the teacher will be able to provide timely help and support for students [1]. Taking as a basis the work of foreign scientists in the field of linguistics and psychology, we can draw a conclusion about the direct relationship between the personal characteristics of students and development of spontaneous speaking skills. Among them are communication skills, empathy, as well as high social communication skills [2].

S. Coopersmith defines self-esteem as "personal assessment the value of oneself as an individual, expressed in a person's attitude towards himself and showing to what extent he believes in his capabilities and how he defines his significance and value for others" [2, p. 34]. According

to a number of foreign scientists, self-esteem manifests itself in all aspects of human activity, including learning foreign languages [4, 7]. Moreover, it is difficult for a person to achieve success or recognition in one activity or another without a certain level of healthy self-esteem, and also sufficient knowledge about yourself and the world around you.

When learning a foreign language, there are two main problems associated with self-esteem: making mistakes in speech and comparing oneself with others. The student admits errors in speech, often comparing themselves with those students who are more successful in mastering a foreign language, which causes the student to lose not only self-esteem, but also motivation to study a foreign language. In such cases, teachers can come to the rescue, capable of relieving psychological difficulties in the process of learning a foreign language, 69 since it is necessary to achieve a psychologically comfortable atmosphere in the classroom, promoting cooperation and co-creativity between students and the teacher [3].

Thus, it is necessary to pay special attention to affective factors when teaching a foreign language to students, since it is teachers who are capable of not only relieve psychological stress in class, but also help students effectively master a foreign language, thereby significantly increasing self-esteem students.

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